

ISSUES IN THE CIVIL LAW REGULATION OF SECURITY ACTIVITIES

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ABSTRACT

This article examines the problems of civil law regulation of security activities in the context of modern market economy development. Particular attention is paid to the legal nature of security activity, its dual (public and private law) character, and the participation of security entities in civil law relations. The study analyzes gaps and inconsistencies in current legislation, including issues related to licensing, organizational and legal forms of security organizations, the definition of security objects, and the legal nature of the security contract. The article substantiates the need to improve civil legislation in order to ensure equality of participants, promote competition, and enhance the effectiveness of protection of civil law objects..

In the conditions of a modern market economy, security activities are emerging as an important institution ensuring the safety of property and non-property relations in society. In particular, the expansion of private property, the increase in the number of business entities, and the growing complexity of economic relations further intensify the demand for security services. This, in turn, determines the relevance of properly and effectively regulating this sphere from a civil-law perspective.

The specific feature of security activity is that it simultaneously represents both a type of entrepreneurial activity and a socially significant activity aimed at ensuring safety. Therefore, this activity is formed within the system of civil-law relations as a special type of service-related obligation. However, in practice it can be observed that the norms regulating security activities in the current legislation are often not fully consistent with the principles of civil legislation.

In particular, the legal nature of security relations combines elements of both public and private law. Certain restrictions on the principle of freedom of contract, disproportions regarding the equality of subjects, and the lack of a clearly developed scientific and legal approach to the legal nature and content of the security contract are among the main problems in this field.

At the same time, the precise legal definition of the concept of a “protected object” and its place in the system of civil-law objects, the organizational and legal status of security entities, their liability, and issues related to the content of contractual relations have not been

sufficiently studied. This leads to various interpretations and contradictions in law-enforcement practice.

The existence of these problems determines the necessity of conducting a profound scientific analysis of the civil-law regulation of security activities, clarifying their legal nature and functions, and developing scientifically grounded proposals for improving legislation.

From this point of view, the study of problems related to the civil-law regulation of security activities has not only theoretical but also practical significance, as it contributes to ensuring the security, stability, and efficiency of civil circulation.

Since this article represents the result of the author's conceptual research on security activities in the sphere of civil-law regulation, it should meet the established criteria. One of these criteria is determining the relevance of the studied problem from the standpoint of its "political, socio-economic, cultural, or economic significance," which is determined by its influence on the development of the state.

This circumstance also determined the purpose of the article, namely, to identify the problems of legal regulation of security activities that have arisen due to inconsistencies with civil legislation and as a result of the process of its improvement.

To achieve this goal, it is necessary to solve the following tasks:

to determine the modern significance of security activities and the degree of their impact on the development of the country;

to identify and classify the problems of legal regulation of security activities and propose ways to eliminate them in accordance with the dynamics of development of civil legislation.

The conducted analysis makes it possible to classify the relevance of security activities on the basis of two criteria.

In particular, attention should also be paid to the importance of security activities in the implementation of constitutional norms. In this respect, they can contribute to solving problems both in the sphere of protecting the foundations of the constitutional system and in ensuring the realization of other constitutional rights of citizens. For example, security activities may manifest themselves as one of the forms of protection of private, state, and municipal property, as well as contribute to the implementation of people's power by ensuring order during referendums and elections.

Security activities are aimed at generating profit through the performance of security work (provision of services), and thus they also contribute to the realization of citizens' right to engage in entrepreneurial activity.

The second criterion determining the relevance of security activities is related to the influence of their private-law nature on the implementation of public functions of the state and on solving other socio-economic tasks, including the implementation of state target programs.

The analysis makes it possible to classify the problems of civil-law regulation of security activities on the following grounds:

First, problems related to inconsistencies with the basic provisions (principles) of civil legislation;

Second, problems related to the imperfection of the organizational and legal form of security organizations;

Third, problems related to the concept of the “protected object”;

Fourth, contractual problems.

Now let us consider these problems from the standpoint of improving civil legislation.

It is known that civil legislation is based on its fundamental initial provisions (Article 1 of the Civil Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan), which also constitute the principles of this branch of law. According to A. Ya. Ryzhenkov, the main problem in applying this article lies not in its content but in its application in the activities of participants of civil circulation and in judicial practice.¹

In this respect, security activities are not an exception. For example, currently the licensing procedure applies only to private security organizations, while departmental and interdepartmental security organizations do not require licensing. Such a situation contradicts the principle of recognition of equality of participants in civil legislation and does not correspond to the constitutional foundations concerning equal protection of all forms of property.

From the standpoint of implementing the principles of civil legislation, it is necessary to eliminate problems in the legal regulation of certain types of security activities. Their essence lies in the fact that regulation in this sphere lags behind the needs of civil circulation, since the main attention is focused on individual types of security activities.

On the one hand, the security contract is not included in the list of contracts provided for in the Civil Code; that is, it does not belong to the category of named contracts and has not been sufficiently studied in civil law. On the other hand, the subject matter and other essential conditions of this contract are not clearly defined in other acts of civil legislation. This often makes it difficult to determine what criteria the parties must agree upon in order for the contract to be considered concluded.

Another problem concerns the organizational and legal form of security organizations as legal entities. Article 13 of the Law “On Security Activities” clearly defines the circle of subjects entitled to carry out security activities on a contractual basis. According to this norm, the authority to carry out such activities mainly belongs to state bodies — the National Guard, the Ministry of Defense, and the Ministry of Internal Affairs. Although this norm appears to ensure the institutional regulation of security services, its civil-law analysis reveals a number of theoretical and practical problems.

First of all, the article provides for the implementation of security activities on a contractual basis, which indicates the civil-law nature of these relations. That is, relations concerning the provision of security services arise through contracts between legally equal subjects rather than through the exercise of state authority. In this sense, the National Guard, the Ministry of Defense, and the Ministry of Internal Affairs participate in these relations not as subjects of public authority but as subjects of civil law (service providers).

However, the problem lies in the fact that these entities are state bodies whose legal status, financial resources, and powers fundamentally differ from those of private security organizations. As a result, in the provision of services on a contractual basis:

real legal equality between the parties may not be ensured;

¹ Ryzhenkov, A. Ya. On the Significance and Composition of the Fundamental Principles of Civil Law / A. Ya. Ryzhenkov // *Legal Policy and Legal Life*. – 2013. – No. 2. – pp. 29–36.

competition in market relations may be restricted;
state entities may occupy a dominant position.

This situation may contradict one of the fundamental principles of civil law — the principle of equality of participants.

Another problem related to the organizational and legal form is that the provision of security services on a contractual basis is mainly carried out by state bodies or organizations established in forms limited by law. This creates a serious problem regarding the organizational and legal forms of security organizations.

The essence of this problem is manifested in the following aspects.

First, granting the right to provide security services only to a limited circle of entities restricts the full functioning of market mechanisms, since from the standpoint of civil law service activities should generally be carried out within the framework of free entrepreneurship.

Second, the organizational and legal forms of security organizations are limited in practice, and the possibilities of their establishment and operation are not equal for all subjects. This affects:

the equality of participants in civil circulation,
freedom of contract,
freedom of entrepreneurship.

Third, when state bodies provide security services on a contractual basis, they act simultaneously in two capacities — public and private-law. This creates legal complexity and raises several questions:

Is a state body a fully equal participant in the contract?
Or does it indirectly use its administrative powers?

The analysis of Article 13 of the law shows that although the mechanism for implementing security activities on a contractual basis corresponds to civil-law relations, its current regulation does not fully comply with the fundamental principles of civil law due to the limited circle of subjects, the dominant participation of state bodies, and the insufficient diversification of organizational-legal forms.

From this point of view, in order to improve the civil-law regulation of security activities, it is necessary to expand the circle of subjects, create a competitive environment, and ensure legal equality between state and private entities.

All the elements of the contract mentioned above require conceptual research taking into account the improvement of civil legislation, since problems related to them often limit the ability of courts to resolve disputes arising in the process of fulfilling contractual obligations correctly and uniformly.

For example, a court of first instance incorrectly concluded that the contract for the provision of security services had not been concluded because the parties had not reached an agreement on the duration of the services. However, the appellate court concluded that this condition is not essential, since the only essential condition of a security contract, as a type of paid service contract, is its subject matter.

In conclusion, it should be noted that at present there are many gaps and contradictions in the legal regulation of security activities. In many cases, the existing regulatory legal acts in

this field are not sufficiently coordinated with each other, which hinders the development of civil legislation.

The main directions for improving the legal regulation of security activities should include clarifying the legal status of security organizations, determining the legal status of protected objects, and defining the legal nature of the security contract, its subject matter, and other essential conditions.

In order to resolve the problems identified above, it is proposed to develop certain amendments to the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On Security Activities” within the framework of improving civil legislation. The separate provisions of this law should reflect the results of this research as well as the findings of other scientific studies devoted to the civil-law nature of security activities.

